
Article

Romantic Individualism and Reactionary Care in Speculative Environmental Fiction

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Abstract

Speculative environmental fiction can inscribe reactionary responses to ecological crises even without intending to. This article examines Shinkai Makoto's 2019 film and novel *Weathering with You* to show how it inadvertently encodes what I term reactionary care: an individualistic and escapist disposition toward environmental crises that diminishes collective human responsibility for both their causes and their consequences. Two mechanisms drive this encoding in this case. First, the story displaces causal responsibility away from human agency by attributing climatic disruption to supernatural forces. Second, it naturalizes individual emotional fulfilment over collective welfare by subordinating environmental engagement to the protagonists' romantic bond as if the two were mutually exclusive. This work of fiction acknowledges a situation of environmental crisis but its representation of causes and consequences demotes it beneath a desire for romantic intimacy as if the two were incompatible.

Keywords: speculative fiction; climate change; romance; narrative; reactionary

1. Introduction

This paper provides a study of Shinkai Makoto's *Tenki no ko*, hereafter *Weathering with You*, its official title in English translation. This work of fiction explores a common ethical problem within environmental thought: the dilemmas of reconciling individual wishes and needs with collective responsibilities and duties against a backdrop of abnormal climate conditions. It analyses how the story attributes climate alterations to supernatural forces and relies on conventional romantic tropes to explain the characters' attitudes and responses to the unfolding disaster. In doing so, it inadvertently suggests a reactionary understanding of environmental care, which rests on individualist and escapist attitudes towards tackling crises.

Weathering with You follows the relationship between two teenagers: Morishima Hodaka, who at the beginning of the story has just run away from his hometown in rural Japan, and Amano Hina, a *hare onna* or 'weather maiden'—a girl with the power to clear the skies of clouds by praying.¹ They meet and develop feelings for each other as Tokyo experiences increasingly long periods of rainfall, leading up to a catastrophic event at the climax. Hodaka and Hina make money using her abilities, charging small fees to disperse the rain on demand. However, the more Hina uses her power, the more severe the climate disruptions become and the greater the toll on her health. Her body slowly turns into water and threatens to evaporate if she continues manipulating the weather, which is at the same time becoming more unruly because of her interventions. When Hina realizes

Received: 20 March 2026

Revised: 15 June 2026

Accepted: 23 June 2026

Published: 25 June 2026

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the need to sacrifice herself to prevent complete climate chaos, the two teenagers refuse this scenario. They reject her martyrdom, deeming their romantic bond too powerful to break. This decision, however, implies the continuation of abnormal weather patterns, which result in Tokyo sinking under rising tides.

Shinkai released *Weathering with You* simultaneously in 2019 as an animated movie and a novel. The movie was a huge commercial success. According to the Motion Picture Producers Association of Japan, it became the highest-grossing film in Japan in 2019. It made over 200 million dollars worldwide, screened in over 140 countries, and represented Japan at the 2020 Academy Awards. The novel, published by Kadokawa, sold over 600,000 copies by the end of its first year. *Weathering with You* follows the successful path of the other two works in Shinkai's so-called disaster trilogy, *Kimi no na wa*, or *Your Name* (Shinkai 2016), and *Suzume no Tojimari*, or *Suzume* (Shinkai 2023), both also stories of teenage love in the face of impending catastrophe. This paper produces a narratological study of its plot and themes and therefore treats both the film and the novel as a single narrative object, omitting any examination of media-specific traits. The two versions of the story are practically identical, with a few small but significant differences that are addressed in the close reading.

This study focuses specifically on how the fictional treatment of issues of care, both interpersonal and human-nonhuman, relates to adaptation, responsibility, and agency when facing environmental degradation, in this case, climate alterations. First, this study examines how *Weathering with You* portrays responses to climate change as driven by individual agency rather than collective action. The story sidesteps human responsibility concerning environmental alterations by attributing these changes to supernatural forces, eliding meaningful discussion about the role of anthropogenic interventions in the degradation of the environment. Second, the narrative's central romantic plot and its treatment of isolated interpersonal relationships end up favoring an interpretation of the role of individual agency that relies on escapism over systemic change and collective commitment. This analysis aims to show how the story's treatment of environmental themes promotes detachment and an uncritical acceptance of the status quo under the guise of adaptation to environmental degradation.

Disasters in fiction can create the space for the reimagination of structures and dynamics of care. This transformative potential attracts authors who see in moments of catastrophic rupture the opportunity to imagine a different world, one that would harbor a more encompassing, open, and just definition of interpersonal and multi-species care, particularly in works of speculative environmental fiction like Becky Chambers's *Monk and Robot* series (Chambers 2025) or Hayao Miyazaki's *Kaze no tani no Naushika* or *Nausicaä of the Valley of the Wind* (Miyazaki 1984) (Heise 2008; Wray and McKay 2023). Other works, like Fernanda Trías's *Mugre Rosa [Pink Slime]* (Trías 2020) or Bong Joon-ho's *Snowpiercer* (Bong 2013), pursue similar ends through the critical reimagination of a worsening of the current dynamics of care, opting for a dystopian critique that would promote a reevaluation of the current politics to avoid such an outcome. As Eva Horn says, "catastrophe thus enables a particular form of experimental knowledge: it demonstrates whether certain bonds are sustainable and whether certain forms of solidarity are possible, while also revealing which all-too-human impulses—weakness, egoism, or even cruelty—must also be considered" (Horn 2018, p. 96). There are, however, other instances in which this transformative potential takes the form of a validation of conservative or reactionary proposals. These are narratives that react to catastrophic disruption with an entrenchment in patriarchal norms. Rather than projecting more balanced approaches to care or shining a critical light on the potential of traditionalist structures, these stories validate traditional forms. They either defend current conventional structures or idealize a return to patriarchal roles and dynamics, acting, explicitly or implicitly, as a reactionary

force against progress and the quest for intersectional social justice through the banal naturalization of an unequal status quo.

The present study establishes a subtle but significant distinction between ‘reactionary’ and ‘conservative’ care. Conservative care aims to sustain existing practices and relationships, often drawing on selective interpretations of what its supporters believe are the historical or cultural traditions of a community. It emphasizes sustaining current systems rather than transforming them, and, in doing so, it forestalls the potential transformative qualities of crises. Conservative forces are concerned with the degree, scale, or speed of the transformations and, while they might accept the need for some level of change or improvement, their approach is cautious, dismissive of transformations, and selective (Celis and Childs 2014). Reactionary care emerges instead as a response to perceived crises or threats. It often seeks to transform romanticized structures, dynamics, and relationships in response to threats such as disasters, but in a way that reifies gender, class, and racial distinctions (Hultman and Pulé 2018). Reactionary care, therefore, leads to more individualistic and hierarchical approaches that lean towards Hobbesian takes on societal organization (Horn 2018, pp. 94–95; MacGregor and Paterson 2021, p. 203). In the context of environmental thought, this position can lead, in its most extreme manifestations, to the spread of ‘ecofascist’ positions (Moore and Roberts 2022, p. 5).

Conservative and reactionary care share similar traits, like claiming traditional gender roles and an appraisal of individual agency over collective action. The main difference is that reactionary care emerges in narratives of environmental degradation as a false alternative to adaptation to the consequences of crises. Conservative positions suggest a slowing down, resizing, or reconfiguration of who deserves the attention and to what extent. On the other hand, as Kay (2024) explains in studying the reactionary turn in some sectors of popular feminism, reactionary positions show traits like regressive logics or bio-essentialism, and are skeptical of—even hostile to—processes of collective transformation. Moreover, reactionary care represents an entrenchment of traditional values and an implicit belief in atomized relationships. It reinforces individualistic dynamics while idealizing patriarchal gender roles under the guise of romantic love. While the push for a reactionary agenda can be an explicit goal by authors, in many cases, it is inadvertently encoded in the themes represented in a story, like the trope of the hypermasculine lone hero in Cormac McCarthy’s *The Road* (McCarthy 2006) or the deeply problematic sympathetic misanthropy of the villain Thanos in Marvel’s *Avengers* universe (James 2020, pp. 38–39). As this article demonstrates, *Weathering with You* fits within this line of unwitting reaffirmation of reactionary dynamics. Its focus on the supernatural as an explanation for environmental alterations and the emotional affordances of romantic love work to displace human responsibility for environmental degradation from view.

2. The Supernatural as a Displacement of Responsibility

Weathering with You is a reluctant work of cli-fi, as it follows Goodbody and Johns-Putra’s formula of inviting audiences to explore “phenomenon not just in terms of setting, but with regard to psychological and social issues, combining fictional plots with meteorological facts, speculation on the future and reflection on the human-nature relationship” (Goodbody and Johns-Putra 2018, p. 2). It centers its conflict around abnormal weather patterns, forcing characters to acknowledge consequences, confront the threats involved in the proliferation of such risks, and attempt to adapt to their changing world. However, despite depicting a scenario rooted in increasingly violent and unusual climate patterns and despite featuring characters who question their role in stopping this phenomenon, *Weathering with You*’s imagination of supernatural forces behind weather alterations displaces human responsibility for environmental degradation. By portraying human agency in the face of an altered climate as inherently limited, the story anchors a

message that prioritizes individualist priorities—romantic fulfillment—over collective responsibilities—a call to reflect on the social and systemic dimension of environmental challenges. It acknowledges the existence of global warming and climate change, and then brings this premise to the background, offering instead supernatural explanations for both the causes and the solutions to these crises.

Weathering with You's diegetic reality closely resembles the world of its viewers. Shinkai meticulously recreates modern Tokyo, emphasizing real-world locations, with several panoramic views of urban landscapes from the city and some of its most iconic spots. It also features ordinary practices and detailed behaviors that are situated in a contemporary context, like posting questions in online forums and doing job-hunting in Yahoo! Japan, or even showing real-world companies like McDonald's. In this regard, the story departs from realism only in the explanation it gives for the abnormal weather. It suggests the existence of a parallel cloud-world, inhabited by mysterious aquatic creatures set right above Tokyo. The specifics of this cloud-world remain fuzzy and ambiguous, and questions like how long it has existed, whether it only covers Japan, or whether these creatures are different from regular aquatic species remain unexplained throughout the narrative, trusting the audience to rely on vague cultural threads to sustain this fiction. The *hare onna*, or weather maidens, are tied to this alternative realm. According to their lore, they are regular young women who are destined to acquire the power to mediate with the weather at certain key junctures in history, acting as mediators between the human and nonhuman worlds.

Stories where a teenager is chosen to act as an intermediary with a parallel world fall within the conventions of a subgenre of Japanese speculative fiction known as *isekai*. This subgenre is particularly popular in content geared for young adults, especially manga, video games, and anime, particularly since the turn of the century. More relevant for this case study, *isekai* narratives often promote escapism and detachment from social issues (Lu 2020): they present a narrative where an individual can evade real-life responsibilities and societal pressures, even if it leads to indulging in the acquisition of new, grandiose duties. These responsibilities are tied to rites of passage that constitute easy switches that allow the characters to go back and forth between the realms. In the case of *Weathering with You*, the characters access the cloud-world through a *torii*, traditional Shinto shrine gate, perched atop a skyscraper. Hina acquires her powers by crossing through this door at the beginning of the story, and this gateway reappears in the third act when Hodaka crosses it too to rescue her. Doors and other elements of transition are a common device in *isekai* fiction and appear also in Shinkai's other movies, taking a central role in *Suzume*. These spatial markers effectively separate what is supposed to be considered normal from an altered space, making it easier to differentiate between two states, a before and after (Yoneyama et al. 2026), a 'here' and 'there' that legitimizes another dichotomy: characters in these narratives have their agency located within one of the realms and are thus exempted from engaging with greater responsibility in the 'regular' world, justifying passivity and an acceptance of the status quo.

Furuhata Yuriko provides one of the most compelling readings of *Weathering with You's* mythological framing, which approaches its mixing of the supernatural and the meteorological as a serious engagement with the epistemic paradoxes of the Anthropocene. For Furuhata, the invented myth of the weather maiden and the symbolic threshold of the shrine gate function as "cultural techniques" through which the narrative "grapples with" the difficulty of distinguishing human history from geohistory, even attempting "to restore both cosmological and meteorological order to the world" (Furuhata 2022, pp. 71–72). In this reading, supernaturalism is not an evasion of the climate crisis but a locally situated mode of thinking it, that is, a "provincial" response to the universalizing, Eurocentric tendencies of Anthropocene discourse (Furuhata 2022, p.

85). This study does not dispute that the story's myth can be read in these terms. The disagreement emerges at the level of register. Furuhashi reads the mythological apparatus for what it allows us to think about the Anthropocene as an epistemic problem, while the present analysis addresses the model of care and responsibility the narrative encodes for its audience. Read at this level, the same mythological framing that Furuhashi recovers as epistemically productive is working, at the narrative level, to displace causal responsibility. It routes the explanation of climatic disruption through supernatural agency and subordinates solving the crisis to the resolution of a romantic bond. Furuhashi's own identification of this work with the *sekai-kei* genre, in which "the apocalyptic crisis of Japan as a nation stands in for the entire world, against which the love story of star-crossed lovers plays out" (Furuhashi 2022, p. 85) aligns with this subordination, even as her reading declines to draw its ethical and political consequences. This paper takes precisely those consequences, the diffusion of collective accountability beneath individual feeling, as its main concern.

The story's mix of realism and supernatural elements can be understood through a different reading, more rooted in the study of the challenges of representing the climate crisis in fiction. Climate change's spatial and temporal scale often "elude everyday social experience [...] we may have to endure extreme weather events, but it is impossible to perceive (as opposed to understand conceptually) how such events reflect broader transformations in the Earth system" (Caracciolo 2022, p. 139). Hina's repeated use of her powers worsens the weather anomalies, but it is unclear why this happens or even how and when deviations in the climate appeared initially. This narrative choice does not deny the reality of anthropogenic climate change, but it displaces its sources: rather than dwelling on the human causes, the narrative attributes climatic alterations to supernatural forces, foregrounding the mystical and leaving the material in the background. However, it provides no coherent explanation for these weather patterns: both the characters and the audience fail to gain any significant understanding of the environment despite having been presented with a state of general deterioration. By framing climate alterations as mystical phenomena, apparently beyond any rational or scientific accounting for their harms, the story avoids addressing the complex socio-economic factors contributing to environmental degradation. It is perfectly possible to resort to the speculative as a genre to bring up reflection on real-world challenges, and indeed, there is potential especially among younger audiences for speculative fiction to become "an ontological tool" that can enable the imagination of "possible worlds in response to the challenges of climate change, and more broadly, the changing material conditions of living in the Anthropocene" (Rousell et al. 2017, p. 655). The problem emerges when the framing behind these speculative stories dislocates debates over responsibility and accountability because of its reliance on supernatural *deus ex machina* explanations for why the environment has worsened.

In a key exposition scene, a Shinto priest, presented as an expert on *hare onna*, tells the characters that it is the job of these girls to "fix the weather" (Shinkai 2019a). Asked whether the current bout of altered weather is in any way exceptional, he dismisses the abnormality as part of natural cycles, claiming that historical weather records are too recent to be trustworthy, and concluding that "we can't even tell what's normal and what's not" (Shinkai 2019a). The narrative does not present the priest as authoritative: he is a figure out of his depth and the narrative neither corroborates nor explicitly rebuts him. The point is not that Shinkai endorses his position, but that such naturalizing rhetoric circulates within the story unchallenged, contributing to the broader displacement of causal responsibility. Left uncorrected, the priest's appeal to natural cycles does the quiet work of dislocating the weather from any human or systemic cause. This displacement

leaves individual initiative and individual concern as the only available model of response.

Yoneyama Shoko argues in her reading of *Weathering with You* that this work provides “a cultural frame of reference that helps us imagine a new kind of human-nature relationship” as “there is no doubt that the Anthropocene, which encapsulates climate change and abnormal weather, constitutes the social and ecological milieu in which this story unfolds” (Yoneyama 2020, pp. 3–4). This paper argues, however, that references to climate change and its impacts in the naturalization of extreme events are indeed recognized diegetically, but then brought to the background, downplayed, or framed as banal. Interestingly, they also constitute a point of salient difference between the film and the novel, where the text gives readers more of the work’s ecological milieu. Right after Hina and Hodaka start their sky-clearing business, the novel shows a series of emails from interested clients. One of them, which only appears in the novel, is written by a fifteen-year-old who complains that “it’s been raining all summer this year,” acknowledging that “with global warming and climate change and temperatures are getting extreme,” a situation which is “becoming the new normal.” This teenager even concedes that “it’s a big problem” but immediately pivots to “an even bigger problem: I’m in love with an older boy at my school!” (Shinkai 2019b, p. 103). This client then requests a clear sky so that they can watch a meteor shower and declare her feelings. This passage shows that the story is fully capable of naming anthropogenic climate change explicitly: “global warming,” “the new normal,” “a big problem.” The issue is that, in the same breath, it subordinates them to Hina’s power: the teenager’s pivot from “it’s a big problem” to the “even bigger problem” of being in love stages in miniature the larger structure of the narrative, in which the environmental crisis is displaced beneath a romantic story. Similarly, Hodaka mentions at the end of the novel his desire to “study something that would be necessary in this era, now that the climate has changed,” opting for agriculture studies at the university (Shinkai 2019b, p. 247). The film buries Hodaka’s explicit ambition in a passing image where the attentive viewer can identify a leaflet from the Department of Agriculture defining their programs as “Education for a New Geological Age” (*aratana chisetsu nendai no kyoiku*) (Shinkai 2019a). Back in the novel, Hodaka frames this goal, however, as insufficient. He worries in that same paragraph that he had yet to find “the really important thing,” the “reason for going to see her, and what I can do for her” (Shinkai 2019b, p. 247), referring to his reencounter with Hina three years after the climax of the narrative.

Finally, *Weathering with You* expresses this displacement through persistent fatalism. After the climax of the third act, when the teenagers decided against Hina’s sacrifice and accepted that the strange weather would continue indefinitely, the story makes a temporal jump of three years in the future. In this epilogue, Tokyo is shown to be partially submerged in its bay. The character of Suga Keisuke, who edits a sensationalist magazine and acts as a surrogate father for Hodaka, seems to represent the general attitude of the citizens of Tokyo towards their new circumstances. In their last conversation of the movie, Suga dismisses Hodaka’s concerns about the fate he and Hina have brought to the land, saying “the world has always been crazy anyway” (Shinkai 2019a). This resignation is then further underpinned by Hodaka’s response to these words, when he validates and extends this position by saying that “the world has always been crazy, so it’s no one’s fault that it’s like this” (Shinkai 2019a). The process of displacement of responsibilities is completed.

3. Romantic Love as Ecological Escapism

Weathering with You contributes to a narrative that prioritizes individual struggles and personal relationships over collective action. The story atomizes relationships into

single-point connections or very close-knit communities, frail and governed by self-absorbed motivations that define allegiances to each other against the backdrop of an indifferent and largely detached social context. While there is an element of non-conventionality associated with these communities, as they show bonds of affection and care that are not strictly based on blood ties—for instance, the aforementioned father-son relationship between Suga and Hodaka—the core of the conflict still relies on a narrow and reactionary understanding of gender roles and the position of individuals towards society at large.

The story suggests that romantic love is enough to overcome catastrophic environmental consequences and that the bond between two people is worth prioritizing above collective welfare. This premise, while emotionally compelling, essentially undermines any potential ecological consciousness inscribed within the narrative's speculative setting. Shinkai presents Hodaka and Hina's relationship as a fated bond between two teenagers whose consequences put the lives and well-being of millions of people at the will of their decisions. In the context of environmental fiction, tropes of romantic love can then encode a reactionary, anti-ecological message: a hierarchy of priorities that places some affective ties above all others, treating them as exclusive. The romantic dyad proposed in *Weathering with You* between Hodaka and Hina explicitly structures a system of care that actively disregards environmental concerns when it clashes with their personal needs. The way the narrative tries to justify the teenagers' decision of putting their bond above the rest is through a framing based on the trope of the transcendent destiny: they were meant to meet, fall in love, and be together, so any attempts to question this arrangement are automatically disregarded, for their bond is, in a diegetic world where the supernatural can be accepted, fated to endure. This logic warps the story's value system in favor of their romantic interests to the extent that even the survival of the whole city, which stands in place of collective interests, cannot match the stakes of their romantic relationship. This narrative suggests that, in the end, individual interests are more important than environmental concerns, even when the stakes are as high as imminent catastrophe.

This encoding becomes clearer when compared with other forms of love and affection, either interpersonal or towards the nonhuman, that are not only compatible with environmental themes, but which can also reinforce them. Miyazaki's *Ponyo* (Miyazaki 2008), also a very popular eco-narrative whose plot revolves around the tensions of maintaining a tie between two individuals that creates the risk of environmental disaster, deals with these questions differently. Ponyo, who starts the movie as a goldfish-like creature, wants to become a human girl, and in this process is helped by a five-year-old boy called Sōsuke. However, this decision unleashes a scenario of growing imbalance between humans and the environment that is eventually settled when Sōsuke reaffirms his commitment to keep loving Ponyo no matter her shape. Granted, the story includes a transformative kiss in the trope of the fairy tale romance, but the two characters are still kids tied by a special dyadic bond and the conflict resolves through an acceptance that requires equal love and respect for human and nonhuman alike. Unlike *Weathering with You*, *Ponyo* resolves its central relationship through ecological integration rather than domination, demonstrating that individual bonds and environmental responsibility need not be opposed.

Weathering with You promotes instead a hierarchical understanding of affective connections that encourages an escapist approach to social strife, diverting attention from broader systemic issues like the climate crisis. By focusing intensely on individual emotional experiences, the story's emphasis on their romantic engagement can create a form of narrative solipsism that privileges personal romantic fulfilment over collective social engagement. It presents love as an achievable product or destination rather than an

ongoing, complex process of mutual understanding and growth. This approach commodifies emotional experiences, reducing deep human connections to marketable, consumable narratives.

Many of the characters have troubled pasts or are suffering from present circumstances that would justify a sense of detachment, apathy, and resentment, emphasizing their isolation. Shinkai systematically gives its characters troubled backgrounds that naturalize a reactionary approach to care: their unresolved traumas legitimate a retreat into atomized relationships rather than engagement with broader social structures. At the beginning of the plot, Hodaka has just run away from home, suggesting a difficult family situation that is never properly explained. Even though by the end he returns to his hometown to finish high school as part of his probation agreement, his family is absent from this process and there is no development of the reasons why the boy escaped from that setting to begin with. The audience is asked to accept without explanation the existence of a grudge that would push the protagonist to escape while underage, try to find a job, and start living at his workplace with strangers. This situation of relative isolation primes him towards single-point connections like traditional romantic partnerships; lacking a larger community or network of caring bonds, Hodaka's isolation makes him more susceptible to hierarchical understandings of care and affection determined by deprivation or fear of loss. Similarly, Hina becomes an orphan at the beginning of the movie, and she is then driven to take care of her younger brother on her own, even though she is barely fifteen years old. Shinkai avoids offering any further explanation about her mother's death, even though it is implied that it coincides with Hina's acquisition of her powers. These backstories create a sense of disconnection from family and society, reinforcing the movie's individualistic framework.

The story presents the metropolitan environment of Tokyo as an inhospitable space for the protagonists through multiple narrative and visual elements. Hodaka encounters significant challenges in accessing basic necessities, including employment or accommodation, upon his arrival. He is undocumented, underage, and alone, with limited funds and no real network of assistance. The audience sees his struggles living in a cybercafé, seeking a job online, and experiencing hunger. He is not alone in facing economic difficulties: Hina is almost hired by a local criminal gang to work at a hostess bar, and Natsumi, Suga's niece and coworker, has as a defining conflict in the movie her search for a proper job. This sense of oppression and precariousness is underpinned too by the urban landscapes. The constant rain creates a gloomy atmosphere that contributes to a demonstrably negative affective response, similarly to the effect of moral and social decay present in noir films and employed in cinematographic depictions of environmental degradation (Fay 2018, p. 98). Tokyo in *Weathering with You* is characterized in its multiple shots of day-to-day interactions and landscape scenes by three primary adverse qualities: excessive population density that leads to anonymity, depersonalized architectural spaces, with a tendency to include abandoned buildings or dark alleyways, and areas of potential criminal activity. King (2021), building on Heise's (2008, p. 61) eco-cosmopolitan awareness, suggests in his work on 'climate' fiction that there is a strong emphasis on reimagining urban locations as spaces that allow for the exploration of interconnection between the human and the nonhuman that is particularly relevant when discussing anthropogenic climate change. These environmental factors function collectively to demonstrate the protagonists' social marginalization and their need to develop autonomous coping mechanisms.

The institutional framework similarly appears as an antagonistic force rather than a supportive structure. Law enforcement authorities actively pursue the protagonists in a subplot involving a gun Hodaka encounters on the street, which serves as a MacGuffin to precipitate the final showdown. The story positions social services, specifically child

protection agencies, as institutional threats to the protagonists' autonomy rather than protective entities, which aligns with the well-documented structural deficiencies of this system in Japan (Udagawa 2022, pp. 119–21). Hina's sudden orphaning and subsequent responsibility for her younger brother are not presented as a systemic failure of social support structures, but rather as a personal challenge that legitimizes her retreat into an individualistic romance. This pattern extends to adult characters, notably through Suga's widowhood and subsequent struggles to restore custody over his daughter. His personal tragedy serves to normalize a cynical detachment from societal obligations, eventually leading him to betray Hodaka to the authorities. These interconnected but isolated traumas create a narrative environment where reactionary care, marked by retreat into personal emotional terrain and rejection of systemic engagement, appears not just justified but inevitable. Rather than presenting the characters' isolation as a problem to be solved through collective action or systemic change, it frames their atomized connections as natural responses to an inherently hostile social world.

Within this scenario of institutional detachment and lack of affective and community bonds, the decision of Hina and Hodaka to turn her powers into a commercial venture acquires another isolationist reading. They manipulate the weather in one direction—the clearing of skies to have sunny days—so that regular economic activities in the city can take place, forging a logic where their small enterprise fits within the large cogs of Tokyo's capitalist machinery. This contributes to the neoliberalization of environmental practices where public services and initiatives are absent, and it is the role of the individual to make a change, for a profit (Clark 2015; Sklair 2020; Bonneuil and Fressoz 2017). In this regard, the narrative already suggests a fatal flaw of this reliance on business initiatives to tackle environmental problems, as it encourages an abuse of Hina's powers that accelerates her—and the climate's—demise.

This story shows Hodaka choosing to save Hina at the cost of Tokyo's climate stability. This decision emphasizes the value of their individual bond over the needs of society as a whole. It suggests that personal happiness trumps environmental concerns, even when the consequences affect millions. The movie romanticizes in this process conventional relationship dynamics based on heteropatriarchal practices and gender expectations. It portrays as admirable Hina's self-sacrificing nature in order to stop the flooding. It also praises Hodaka's desire to be the financial provider for the couple as a noble impulse, even though it arises in reaction to the fact that Hina had been the main income provider through the commercialization of her powers. This reinforcement of traditional gender roles can be seen as regressive, especially in the context of modern environmental challenges that require breaking from old patterns. The story plays a false dichotomy: either Hina is sacrificed and Tokyo is saved, or they reject Hina's martyrdom to be together, even if it is at the expense of environmental collapse. This opposition produces high stakes for their relationship, equating their bond with the fate of the city. It frames Hodaka's decision to cross to the cloud-world to save Hina as heroic, as he evades a frenetic police chase to do so, even though it goes against her wishes. It frames the reasons for rejecting the sacrifice, however, away from condemning the system of martyrdom for being unjust and gendered and instead grounds them on their desire to be together as a couple. In a visually striking scene, as Hina and Hodaka fall from the sky against stormy clouds, reaching for each other's hands, she shows concern for the consequences of their decision, realizing "the weather will go back." Hodaka disregards these fears, shouting that "I'd rather have you than a blue sky" and that "if the weather goes crazy ... it can just stay that way" (Shinkai 2019a). It inflates the price of sacrifice as the only possible solution, but this is just a narrative choice. As seen in the example of *Ponyo*, there are ways to create a climactic turning point around making a decision that

can be based on a more expansive idea of care that balances individual happiness while not foreclosing environmental concerns.

Finally, the story's incorporation of magical elements and its intense focus on the romantic relationship between the two protagonists serve as distractions from the environmental crisis. The narrative's emphasis on the mechanics of supernatural manipulation of the weather and the deep emotional connection between the main characters, while potentially persuasive from a storytelling perspective, draws attention away from the real-world implications of climate change. By encouraging viewers to invest emotionally in the personal journey of the characters at the expense of the broader environmental context, it promotes a hierarchical distribution of concerns—personal over social—that can end up justifying a position of escapism or cynicism. This retreat into personal matters and supernatural solutions potentially encourages a reactionary response to global environmental challenges. It leads viewers to prioritize individual emotional comfort and romantic fulfilment over the critical need for collective action and meaningful engagement with real-world environmental problems. This narrative choice, while perhaps unintentional, contributes to a broader pattern of avoiding direct confrontation with the pressing realities of climate change.

4. Conclusions

This analysis reveals a narrative that encodes a reactionary approach to environmental degradation and interpersonal relationships. *Weathering with You* explores the dilemmas of balancing individual desires and needs with collective actions and responsibilities in the face of environmental degradation. The answer it provides to this problem, however, inadvertently naturalizes a perspective that prioritizes individual emotional gratification over collective environmental responsibility. This story sidesteps any substantive discussion of anthropogenic environmental degradation by deploying the supernatural as an explanation that removes human responsibility for violent climate changes. This narrative strategy can reinforce defeatist positions that deflect large-scale anthropogenic accountability for real-world environmental damage and encourage a fatalistic acceptance of environmental catastrophe. Its portrayal of adaptation is also reductive. The partial submersion of Tokyo is presented as an inevitable outcome that emerges without an exploration of the challenges involved in adapting the largest metropolis on the planet to this new condition. This logic can dampen proactive environmental engagement, promoting instead a passive acceptance that serves only to reinforce existing social structures or to suggest climate adaptation can take place independent of individual engagement.

Central to the story's reactionary narrative is its treatment of interpersonal relationships, particularly romantic love. It positions the relationship between Hodaka and Hina as a force that transcends collective well-being, with their individual emotional bond taking precedence over the potential environmental catastrophe affecting millions. This narrative choice reflects a problematic understanding of care that is atomized and individualistic. The protagonists' decision to prioritize their personal relationship over societal welfare is emblematic of a reactionary form of care that retreats into personal emotional spaces rather than confronting broader social challenges. The dynamics between the characters further reinforce this perspective. Each character is presented as disconnected from broader social structures, marked by personal traumas and institutional alienation. Shinkai depicts Tokyo as inherently hostile and its institutional frameworks as antagonistic forces rather than potential sources of support. This portrayal encourages a view of social interaction that is defensive and self-preserving instead of promoting practices that rely on collaboration or that envision the transformation of the world around them. In a similar vein, the way *Weathering with You* presents gender

dynamics also contributes to its reactionary stance. It subtly reinforces traditional patriarchal gender roles under the guise of a romantic narrative. These narrative choices reveal a conservative understanding of gender relations that conflicts with more progressive approaches to interpersonal dynamics. Both the supernatural elements and intense romantic focus serve another critical function: they provide a mechanism of narrative escapism. By encouraging viewers to invest emotionally in the romantic plot of the protagonists and to accept mystical explanations for how to solve weather alterations that rely on individual sacrifice or heroism, it diverts attention from the collective dimension of the causes and solutions to tackle environmental damage.

Ultimately, *Weathering with You* represents a sophisticated yet concerning approach to environmental narratives. Its proposed model for dynamics and practices of care, based on individualistic and escapist reactions, suggests that, in the face of ecological crisis, the most appropriate response is not collective action or systemic transformation, but individual emotional retreat and the acceptance of things as they are. The story turns away from the potentially transformative space of disaster, what could be an opportunity for reimagining social structures, in favor of a narrative approach that reinforces existing power dynamics. By focusing on personal happiness within the current system rather than challenging societal problems, it arguably reinforces existing social structures and, paradoxically for a work that can imagine supernatural manipulation, constrains the imagination of how we might tackle this crisis and envision alternative modes of caring about the weather and each other. The story concludes with Hodaka shouting an optimistic “Bokutachi wa kitto daijōbu”, that is, “I’m sure we’ll be fine!” (Shinkai 2019a). Yoneyama reads this call as a positive affirmation of their desire to live together while keeping Donna Haraway’s motto of staying with the trouble (Yoneyama 2020, p. 12), but this analysis offers an alternative reading that argues their understanding of communality is still limited to their mutual construction as a dyadic romantic bond that isolates them rather than expanding to other forms of community. This position summarizes the political stance of the narrative: despite the dire circumstances, *Weathering with You* reinforces an individualistic approach to a global crisis. It offers what appears to be an optimistic but arguably insufficient perspective that everything will be alright.

Funding: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101146614.

Data Availability Statement: No new data were created or analyzed in this study. Data sharing is not applicable to this article.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

Note

- ¹ I follow the conventions of Japanese names (Last Name + First Name), but will refer to the characters by their given name, as that is the most used in the stories.

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